

such as textbooks and learning modules should also include cultural elements to develop students' intercultural communicative competence. Mandarin as a foreign language (MFL) courses has gained popularity among non-native speakers in local higher education institutions (HEIs) as the enrolment for this course has risen. However, there does not seem to be studies determining whether cultural elements are incorporated in the course and in the textbooks used. This study investigates whether the cultural and intercultural are incorporated elements in MFL textbooks from seven selected public HEI in Malaysia¹. Directed content analysis is used based on the cultural and intercultural framework for communication. The findings indicate that there were insufficient cultural and intercultural elements in most of the sampled textbooks. This means that in future, textbooks written for MFL should include cultural and intercultural elements for better understanding of the language.

Main body: Language does not exist in isolation but is part of a society and culture. This is especially true for foreign language instruction where language and culture are intertwined and cannot be separated. Communication between people of different cultural background may be misunderstood in an intercultural setting, as interpretations are based on assumptions and perceptions from one's own culture. Distinction of vocabulary, syntax, language styles, non-verbal behaviour, values, beliefs, as well as customs between cultures could also cause conflicts and misunderstanding during intercultural communication. Thus, using a language without understanding the cultural background may lead to misunderstandings and conflicts². Cultural content for teaching MFL was divided into two categories from

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² Brislin, 1995; Hammer, 1999; Wolfson, 1989

